

Preprint: Redistributive Preferences, Social Dominance Orientation, and Emotional Responses to Economic Inequality across Welfare Regimes

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Abstract

This paper proposes a nuanced examination of the variability of emotional responses to different aspects of economic inequality across different types of welfare regimes. The primary objective is to identify systematic differences or similarities in emotional responses across various stimuli of economic inequality, namely income inequality and wealth inequality. Subsequently, we focus on potential antecedents of these emotions, considering social dominance orientation and system-justifying beliefs such as meritocracy and belief in a just world, as well as potential consequences such as redistributive preferences. We administered an online questionnaire to nation-wide samples in France and Great Britain ($n = 3000$ per country). We collected data on eight different types of emotions experienced when considering income and wealth inequality—more specifically: sadness, moral outrage, anger, indifference, frustration, compassion, contentment, and admiration. Our findings show that stronger endorsement of SDO and system-justifying beliefs was consistently associated with lower support for redistribution. Mediation analyses revealed that this relationship is partly explained by emotional responses to economic inequality—and fully explained in the case of BJW. Specifically, moral outrage and indifference emerged as the most robust and consistent mediators across all models, while compassion played a mediating role in the majority of the models. These findings underscore the psychological pathways through which ideological beliefs shape public support for redistribution and highlight the central role of affect in legitimizing or challenging economic inequality.

Keywords: Redistribution, Social Dominance Orientation, System-justification beliefs, Emotions, Income and Wealth Inequality

Introduction

Perhaps more striking than the growth of economic inequality itself is the widespread lack of resistance or mobilization in response to it. Against expectations, a lesson from social history reveals that rebellion is not the typical reaction to hardship in oppressive systems; rather, most individuals have shown a tendency to tolerate exploitation and remain obedient (Zinn, 1968/2002). From a psychological perspective, this phenomenon may be partially understood through social dominance theory (Sidanius & Pratto, 1999) and system justification theory (Jost & Banaji, 1994). Although distinct, these theoretical frameworks converge on the idea that widely shared legitimizing myths serve as mechanisms that preserve the stability of unequal socioeconomic systems by attenuating individual resistance to such structures (Jost & Hunyady, 2005; Sidanius & Pratto, 1999). Furthermore, individuals who endorse these beliefs may view their relatively deprived position in a more complacent or indifferent light than those who do not endorse such beliefs which, in turn, could result in a muted or largely absent response to inequality (Osborne & Sibley, 2013).

Nevertheless, it is noteworthy that there are personal rewards resulting from supporting hierarchical structures in society and endorsing system-justifying beliefs. Indeed, these beliefs influence how individuals psychologically experience inequality (e.g., it reduces one's psychological distress), a phenomenon often referred to as the psychological benefits or palliative function (Jost & Hunyady, 2003). Thus, those beliefs could serve to shield individuals from the harmful psychological consequences of economic inequality while simultaneously diminishing their support for collective action aimed at addressing it (Osborne & Sibley, 2013).

This study aims to advance our understanding of the psychological mechanisms underlying support for redistributive policies by first examining how Social Dominance Orientation (SDO) and System-justifying Beliefs influence redistributive preferences. In a second step, we seek to explore how emotional experiences related to economic inequality may mediate these relationships. Our central hypothesis is that individuals' affective responses to inequality help explain why those who endorse SDO and system-justifying beliefs are less inclined to support redistribution. By integrating both ideological and emotional dimensions, this research offers a more comprehensive account of the psychological barriers that limit public support for structural change in the face of growing economic disparities.

Social Dominance Orientation and System-justifying Beliefs

The concept of social dominance orientation (SDO) refers to “a general attitudinal orientation toward intergroup relations, reflecting whether the person generally prefers such relations to be egalitarian or hierarchical” (Pratto et al., 1994, p. 742). From the social dominance theory, these

attitudinal orientations have been widely studied for their role in maintaining social hierarchies. Individuals or groups with high SDO prefer and support hierarchical structures in society, and are more likely to justify and perpetuate systems of inequality. By contrast, those with low SDO favour more egalitarian intergroup relations and are generally more supportive of efforts to reduce economic disparities (Jost & Thompson 2000; Rodriguez-Bailon et al., 2017; Sidanius & Pratto, 1999).

System Justification Theory (Jost & Banaji, 1994) represents another influential perspective that continually exchanges ideas with the concept of SDO, focusing on how individuals legitimize and uphold existing social structures (Jost, Banaji, & Nosek, 2004). Traditionally, this phenomenon was studied from a sociological perspective, highlighting how members of dominant groups disseminate ideologies that justify and sustain social hierarchies that promote inequality (Marx & Engels, 1846/1991). However, System Justification Theory posits that individuals are psychologically motivated to uphold these ideological orientations, commonly referred to as “system-justifying beliefs”. A wide range of beliefs may fall under this category (for an overview, see Jost & Hunyady, 2005). For example, the belief that people get what they deserve in life has been extensively studied and is conceptualized as the Belief in a Just World (BJW; Lerner, 1980, 1998; Lerner & Clayton, 2011). Another prominent system-justifying belief is meritocracy, which refers to the notion that individuals’ social and economic outcomes are determined by their own talent and effort (Bartram, 2022; Hadarics et al., 2021). Within this framework, success is attributed to hard work and intelligence, while failure is viewed as the result of personal shortcomings (Young, 1958). Although meritocratic beliefs share with SDO the function of legitimizing social inequalities by offering a sense of fairness and order (Jost & Hunyady, 2005), they are conceptually closer to BJW, while remaining theoretically distinct (see Castillo, 2019).

Overall, research suggests that lower support for redistribution is linked to high endorsement of SDO (Jost & Thompson 2000; Rodriguez-Bailon et al., 2017), BJW (Kugler, Cooper & Nosek 2010; Lipkus & Siegler, 1993; Moore, 2008) and Meritocracy belief (García-Sánchez et al., 2020; Kluegel & Smith, 2017). However, much of this literature has concentrated on the motivational processes through which individuals interpret economic inequality in ways that align with their ideological commitments—actively evaluating, rationalizing, or distorting information to reinforce existing beliefs (Waldfogel et al., 2021). A complementary recent line of research suggests that ideological orientations may not only influence how individuals interpret information, but also shape what kinds of information they attend to and experience. This research suggests that individuals may be exposed to the same environments yet perceive different realities, due to early-stage attentional processes that prioritize information based on

their ideological beliefs (Waldfogel et al., 2021; Phillips et al., 2020). For instance, in an insightful scientific contribution based on five experimental studies, Waldfogel et al. (2021) demonstrate that SDO influences both individuals' attention to inequality and their accuracy in perceiving it. That is, individuals with a lesser tolerance for group-based hierarchies tend to be more vigilant and perceptually attuned to the presence of inequality (Bargh & Pratto, 1986; Moskowitz et al., 2011). Thus, given that ideological commitments can shape not only how we interpret but also what we experience and perceive, the present study examines how differences in SDO may influence the emotional experience of economic inequality and, in turn, reduce redistribution preferences.

Palliative function of system-justifying ideologies

As previously mentioned, System Justification Theory suggests that there is a psychological motivation for individuals to preserve the status quo. The tendency to legitimize social inequalities among both advantaged and disadvantaged group members can be partly explained by the palliative effects this process entails (Jost, 2020). Several studies have supported this hypothesis, suggesting that system justification provides psychological benefits such as satisfaction with one's own socioeconomic status (Jost & Hunyady, 2003), satisfaction with life in general (Li et al., 2020) and enhanced psychological well-being (Harding & Sibley, 2013; Sengupta et al., 2017; Vargas-Salfate, 2019). Although these benefits may be particularly relevant for low-status group members by helping them to better cope with their disadvantaged position (Jost & Hunyady, 2003; for a recent review, see Lima et al., 2024), high-status group members may also benefit from this rationalization. For instance, in a longitudinal survey conducted across 18 countries, Vargas-Salfate et al. (2018) found no significant differences in the psychological well-being derived from system justification as a function of participants' social status.

Evidence suggests that SDO is associated with negative effects elicited by socioeconomic injustice, highlighting a potentially blunting effect on emotional reactions (Bastias & Cañadas, 2021; Kugler et al., 2010; Tan et al., 2015; Wakslak et al., 2007). As for the role of the System-justifying beliefs included in this work, research shows that strong BJW believers experience greater psychological well-being when confronted with negative outcomes than weak believers in a just world (Concha et al. 2012; Correia et al., 2024; McCoy et al. 2013) and lower discontent at the workplace (Hafer & Olson, 1993). Similarly, meritocracy beliefs, understood as an ideology that serves to justify the status quo, may contribute to short-term emotional relief (Hadarics et al., 2021). Taken together, these studies suggest that endorsing SDO and system-

justifying beliefs contribute to greater acceptance of economic inequality and a reduction of psychological distress.

Much of the literature has focused on the links between ideological beliefs and indicators of subjective well-being. However, with a few exceptions (Bahamondes et al., 2019, 2020; Bastias & Cañadas, 2021; Jost et al., 2008; Napier et al., 2020; Wakslak et al., 2007), relatively little is known about how ideological orientations shape individuals' *emotional experiences* in response to economic disparities. In studying this experience, it is essential to consider at least two key points. First, unlike moods or general sentiments, emotions are affective responses to specific stimuli. As Ekkekakis (2013) explains, emotions are “elicited by something, are reactions to something, and are generally about something” (p. 322). Second, in most research on affective states emotional experiences are understood as inherently conscious phenomena (Lambert et al., 2019). In this line, Clore (1994) emphasizes that “it is not possible to have an unconscious emotion because emotion involves an experience” (p. 285). This conceptualization, therefore, has established self-report measures as the primary method for capturing the phenomenological experience of emotion in psychology (Russell & Carroll, 1999). Based on this framework, the present study explores individuals' emotional responses to two specific forms of economic inequality—income inequality and wealth inequality—through participants' own reports of their emotional experience.

Previous research offers indirect support for the idea that emotions modulate the link between system-justifying beliefs and responses to inequality, though direct evidence is limited and has typically focused on a narrow range of specific emotional reactions. To name a few, for instance, a notable study by Wakslak et al. (2007) demonstrated that moral outrage mediates the effect of social dominance orientation on support for resource redistribution. Osborne and Sibley (2013) found that forms of relative deprivation predicted psychological distress, but importantly, this relationship was weaker among individuals with higher levels of system justification. Lastly, Jost and colleagues (2012) investigated how system-justifying beliefs influence individuals' motivation to engage in collective action. Across three studies, they found that both students (study 1) and political activists (studies 2 and 3) showed lower levels of support for protest-related activities when they more strongly endorsed beliefs that justify the existing social system. Importantly, this negative association was explained by a reduction in feelings of anger, which acted as a mediating factor.

To contribute to a better understanding of the psychological mechanisms underlying support for redistributive policies, this paper advances the field by examining how SDO and specific system-justifying beliefs affect redistributive preferences through emotional responses to

economic inequality. To this end, we draw on a carefully selected set of emotion-specific responses to income and wealth inequality, identified through previous qualitative and quantitative research (Bastias & Zmerli, under review).

Methods

Samples

The study included two samples from Great Britain ($n = 3,002$) and France ($n = 3,012$), with quotas established for age, gender, and region. The British sample had a mean age of 48.7 years ($SD = 17.9$, range = 18–94) and an average of 14.7 years of education ($SD = 4.4$), with 47.6% identifying as male, 52.3% as female, and 0.1% as other. Household income was reported in decile categories, with the median income falling within category F (£2,659–£3,162). Similarly, the French sample had a mean age of 48.7 years ($SD = 17.7$, range = 18–95) and a mean of 13.3 years of education ($SD = 3.4$), with 48.4% male, 51.4% female, and 0.2% identifying as other. Household income was also reported in deciles, with the median falling within category G (€2,601–€3,000).

Quality control procedures were implemented to ensure data integrity, including the prevention of duplicate responses, exclusion of participants who completed the questionnaire in less than 25% of the median interview time, and the inclusion of an attention check item. A soft launch was conducted to test survey logic and functionality. The hypotheses guiding the study were preregistered before data collection, which took place in June and July 2024 (https://aspredicted.org/74V_VJK).

Measures

Social Dominance Orientation (SDO) is assessed using a short version of the SDO Scale (Pratto et al., 2013), adapted and validated for France and Great Britain. The question wording was: “*There are many kinds of groups in the world: men and women, ethnic and religious groups, nationalities, political factions. How much are you in favour of or opposed to the ideas about groups in general? Next to each statement, write a number from 1 (Extremely Oppose) to 10 (Extremely Favour) to show your opinion according to this scale*”. The four items were: (1) In setting priorities, we must consider all groups (reverse coded); (2) We should not push for group equality; (3) Group equality should be our ideal (reverse coded); (4) Superior groups should dominate inferior groups. At the end of each statement we also included “Can’t choose” as an option. We obtained a reliability of $\alpha = .64$ for this scale.

Belief in a Just World. Based on Lipkus’s (1991) work, we assessed BJW with the item: “*In [country], people get what they deserve*”. Responses were recorded on a 5-point scale ranging

from 1 (Strongly agree) to 5 (Strongly disagree). We reverse-coded the item for analysis, such that higher scores indicate stronger agreement. We included “Can’t choose” as an answer option.

Meritocratic belief. Based on previous research (Bartram, 2022) and the wording of the item in the European Social Survey (Hadarics et al., 2021), support for meritocracy was assessed with the agreement to the following statement: “*Large differences in people’s incomes are acceptable to properly reward differences in talents and efforts.*” To introduce a novel element, we presented a *second* and reformulated version of this item to half of the sample, focusing on wealth disparities: “*Large differences in people’s wealth are acceptable to properly reward differences in talents and efforts.*” Responses were recorded on a 5-point scale ranging from 1 (Strongly agree) to 5 (Strongly disagree). We reverse-coded the item for analysis, such that higher scores indicate stronger agreement. We also included “Can’t choose” as an answer option.

Emotions. We measured eight emotional responses—anger, moral outrage, contentment, frustration, indifference, compassion, admiration, and sadness—towards two different inequality stimuli—income inequality and wealth inequality. The selection of these emotions was based on prior qualitative and quantitative pre-test analyses (Bastias & Zmerli, under review). Considering that the overt expression of internal states is typically captured using Likert-type scales in psychology (Lambert et al., 2019), we asked participants: “When you think about [stimulus] in [country], to what extent do you feel the following emotions? Please place yourself on a score where 1 means ‘not at all’ and 5 means ‘extremely’” For each emotion, participants also had the option to select “Can’t choose.”

Redistributive Preferences. This variable was measured using a single-item: “*There are a number of opposite views on the issue of taxes and social spending. How would you place your views on this scale from 0 to 10?*” Responses were given on a horizontal 11-point scale ranging from 0 to 10, where the endpoints were defined as follows: 0 = ‘Government should decrease taxes a lot and spend much less on social benefits and services’ and 10 = ‘Government should increase taxes a lot and spend much more on social benefits and services’. We also included “Can’t choose” as an answer option.

Sociodemographic variables. The survey collected demographic information such as age, gender, household income, subjective social status, and educational attainment¹.

¹ See appendix for more information

Data Analysis

We conducted country-specific linear regression analyses to examine the effects of SDO, BJW, and meritocracy beliefs (split by income and wealth inequality frames) on redistributive preferences. Regressions were conducted using R (R Core Team, 2021), with full information maximum likelihood in *lavaan* (Rosseel, 2012). Control Variables were age, gender, household income, education, and subjective social status.

In a second step, we tested whether our set of (eight) emotions towards two different stimuli (income inequality and wealth inequality) mediated the effect of each of our three ideological orientations (SDO, BJW, and Meritocracy) on redistributive preferences, in each country (France and Great Britain). For that, we estimated 12 parallel multiple mediation models (PMMM) using PROCESS Model 4 in SPSS, with 5,000 bootstrap samples (Hayes, 2017). Control variables included in all models were age, gender, education, household income, and subjective social status.

Results

Table 1 displays descriptive statistics for the variables under scrutiny in both Britain and France. In Britain, the mean score for redistributive preferences was significantly higher than in France ($t(5707) = 14.39, p < .001$). SDO showed comparable averages in both countries, with no statistically significant difference ($t(5598) = -1.93, p = .054$). However, small but statistically significant differences were observed for BJW ($t(5767) = -2.72, p = .006$) and meritocracy regarding wealth inequality ($t(2901) = -2.29, p = .022$), both of which were slightly higher in the French sample.

Table 1
Descriptive statistics of the variables under study

	Britain					France				
	N	Min	Max	Mean	SD	N	Min	Max	Mean	SD
Redistributive Preferences	2843	0	10	5.29	2.50	2866	0	10	4.35	2.42
SDO	2781	1	10	3.51	1.82	2829	1	10	3.60	1.76
BJW	2885	1	5	2.63	1.00	2884	1	5	2.71	1.11
Meritocracy (income inequality)	1447	1	5	3.11	1.12	1480	1	5	3.10	1.16
Meritocracy (wealth inequality)	1444	1	5	3.03	1.12	1459	1	5	3.13	1.14

Differences between the two emotional stimuli were also present (see Figure 1). Emotional reactions were generally stronger in response to income inequality than to wealth inequality—particularly for compassion in Great Britain and frustration in both countries. In contrast,

feelings such as admiration, indifference, and contentment were consistently low across the two stimuli, and even lower in France.

Figure 1.

Means of emotions towards Income and Wealth Inequality

In addition, most emotional responses significantly differed between countries, with French respondents generally reporting higher levels of negative emotions than British participants. The only exception was sadness, which did not significantly differ between countries for neither income ($t(2885) = 0.619, p = .536$) nor wealth inequality ($t(2886) = 0.750, p = .454$). French participants were more likely to report moral outrage and anger, especially regarding income inequality, while British respondents expressed higher levels of compassion.

Among the ideological predictors examined (see Figure 2), Social Dominance Orientation (SDO) consistently emerged as the strongest and most reliable negative predictor of support for redistribution across all models² and in both countries (e.g., GB total model: $\beta = -0.44, p < .001$; FR: $\beta = -0.53, p < .001$), indicating that individuals with a higher preference for group-based hierarchies were less supportive of redistributive policies. Belief in meritocracy—both income- and wealth-related—was also significantly and negatively associated with redistribution attitudes in all models (e.g., wealth meritocracy: GB $\beta = -0.46$; FR $\beta = -0.37$; both $p < .001$), suggesting that endorsing merit-based reward systems is linked to weaker support for redistribution. By contrast, Belief in a Just World (BJW) showed weaker and less consistent effects: while it was a significant negative predictor in the full models (GB: $\beta = -0.15, p = .006$; FR: $\beta = -0.10, p = .041$), it was not significant in the income or wealth-specific

² We estimated three separate regression models due to the structure of the survey design: the variables Meritocracy (income) and Meritocracy (wealth) were each presented to only half of the sample as part of a split-ballot design. Accordingly, one model included only Meritocracy (income), another included only Meritocracy (wealth), and a third model ("All") excluded both variables in order to retain the full sample. This approach avoided substantial loss of statistical power and prevented distortions in sample composition that would have resulted from combining split-ballot items into a single model.

models. These results highlight the greater explanatory power of SDO and meritocratic beliefs over BJW in shaping public attitudes toward economic inequality and redistribution in both the British and French contexts.

Figure 2.

Effect of SDO and System-justifying Beliefs on Redistributive Preferences

Note. Coefficients are shown with 95% confidence intervals. The effects of meritocracy (wealth) and Meritocracy (income) are estimated using half the sample each, due to the split-questionnaire design. Controls: age, gender, income, education, and subjective social status.

Across our four PMMM, SDO was consistently associated with lower preferences for redistribution, both directly and indirectly through emotional mediators. In all models, significant indirect effects were observed (total indirect effects ranging from -0.14 to -0.22 for income inequality, and -0.17 for wealth inequality), particularly via emotions such as moral outrage, indifference, and compassion, with the British income model also showing mediation through sadness, anger, and admiration (see Figure 3 and Figure 4).

Figure 3.

Mediators: Emotions towards Income Inequality in Britain (above) and France (below)

The direct effect of SDO on redistributive preferences is negative and robust in France (income: -0.39, wealth: -0.37), and in Britain for wealth inequality (-0.37), but is not statistically significant for income inequality in Britain (-0.13, ns). Overall, the models explain a meaningful proportion of the variance in redistributive preferences (Britain: $R^2 = 0.16-0.17$; France: $R^2 = 0.14-0.15$).

Figure 4.

Mediators: Emotions towards Wealth Inequality in Britain (above) and France (below)

As Figures 5 and 6 depict, the direct effects of BJW on redistributive preferences are not statistically significant in any model. However, BJW is associated with lower preferences for redistribution through indirect effects via emotional mediators, in all models (total indirect effects ranging from -0.07 to -0.26), particularly via emotions such as moral outrage, indifference, and compassion. In the context of income inequality, the British model also shows mediation through sadness, anger, and admiration. This results highlight that the association is largely explained by emotional pathways. The models explain a small to modest proportion of variance in redistributive preferences (Britain: $R^2 = 0.13-0.18$; France: $R^2 = 0.11-0.14$).

Figure 5.

Mediators: Emotions towards Income Inequality in Britain (above) and France (below)

Figure 6.

Mediators: Emotions towards Wealth Inequality in Britain (above) and France (below)

Results shown in Figure 7 and 8 indicate that stronger meritocratic beliefs are associated with lower preferences for redistribution, both directly and indirectly via emotional mediators. In all cases, significant indirect effects are observed (total indirect effects range from -0.13 to -0.31), particularly through emotions such as moral outrage, indifference, and compassion.

Figure 7.

Mediators: Emotions towards Income Inequality in Britain (above) and France (below)

Figure 8.

Mediators: Emotions towards Wealth Inequality in Britain (above) and France (below)

The direct effects of meritocracy on redistributive preferences are also robustly negative (direct effects: Britain income = -0.16, France income = -0.35, Britain wealth = -0.29, France wealth = -0.26), and the overall models explain a substantial portion of variance in redistribution preferences (e.g., R^2 ranges from 0.13 to 0.18).

DISCUSSION

This study aimed to explore the emotional mechanisms linking SDO and system-justifying beliefs to redistributive preferences. Our findings provide compelling support for our hypothesis. Stronger endorsement of SDO and system-justifying beliefs –such as BJW, and meritocracy– was associated with lower support for redistribution across both national samples. Furthermore, the mediation models highlight the powerful role that the emotional experience of inequality plays in this relationship. Notably, SDO and meritocracy displayed the strongest and most consistent total and direct effects across the 12 models (with direct effects reaching up to -0.39), alongside meaningful indirect effects via emotions. By contrast, BJW did not exhibit any significant direct effects on redistribution attitudes; instead, its influence operated entirely through the affective channel. That is, emotional responses serve as the primary pathway through which BJW exerts its influence.

Among the emotions examined as mediators, moral outrage and indifference consistently emerged as robust mediators across all models, highlighting their central role in the affective pathways linking system-justifying beliefs to redistributive preferences. Compassion also played a mediating role, particularly in relation to SDO and Meritocracy. Other emotions, such as sadness, anger, and admiration, proved relevant in specific contexts, especially within the British sample. In contrast, frustration and contentment did not significantly mediate the relationship in any of the models.

A major contribution of this study is its comprehensive assessment of emotional responses to economic inequality. Contrary to previous research that has predominantly focused on particular emotions (Bahamondes et al., 2019, 2020; Bastias & Cañadas, 2021; Jost et al., 2008; Napier et

al., 2020; Wakslak et al., 2007), this study examined a broader set of affective reactions informed by prior qualitative and quantitative evidence (Bastias & Zmerli, under review). Importantly, the inclusion of a diverse set of emotions in the same study allows for a direct comparison between them and a more precise assessment of their relative importance in shaping support for redistribution. In fact, the results underscore the importance of distinguishing between anger and moral outrage. Although both are negative emotions, they differ in their psychological meaning and social implications. Anger can be elicited by economic inequality in general, but it may also arise in response to individual agents—either the disadvantaged or the advantaged—without necessarily implying a moral evaluation of the situation. Moral outrage, by contrast, inherently involves a judgment of an unjust situation and typically reflects a motivation to restore fairness. As such, it is more directly linked to attitudes favouring redistribution.

All models explain a meaningful, though moderate, proportion of variance in redistribution preferences (R^2 between 0.11 and 0.18). Ideological beliefs via emotions account for a notable, yet limited, share of the variance in preferences for redistribution. This indicates the importance of considering additional influences when examining people's redistributive preferences (e.g., trust in government, and political ideology). At the same time, given the complexity of responses to economic inequality, our study explored just one of several pathways that contribute to reduce economic inequality.

To conclude, the evidence suggests that SDO and system-justifying beliefs buffer individuals from the emotional discomfort associated with income and wealth inequality, while simultaneously decreasing their motivation to support structural change. This dual effect—emotional relief and political passivity—illustrates the palliative function of system justification (Jost & Hunyady, 2003). When individuals are exposed to adverse social conditions from which they cannot escape, they may still alter their psychological reality, including the way they emotionally experience such conditions. In this way, system-justifying ideologies may shape not only how people respond or act toward inequality, but also how they feel about it. Taken together, these findings shed light on the psychological barriers that inhibit redistributive preferences, while emphasizing the importance of both attitudinal and affective processes in shaping public support for redistribution.

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